

Customer Perception towards Reliance Jio in Madurai City

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Abstract

Marketing Management is a business discipline which is focused on the practical application of marketing techniques and the management of a firm marketing resources and activities. Traditionally, marketing analysis was structured into three areas like customer analysis, company analysis and competitor analysis. Satisfaction of consumer needs, wants and expectations are the main heart of the marketing management. For customer analysis a study on the customer behaviour is necessary one. Recently, the satisfaction of customer are taken into account 7P's viz., product, price, place, promotion, people process and physical evidence. This paper focused the Customer Perception towards Jio in Madurai City.

Keywords: Reliance Jio, Customer, Perception, Brand

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India has a fast-growing mobile service market with excellent potential for the future. With almost 5million subscribers amassed in less than 2 years of operation. India's growth tempo has far exceeded that of numerous other markets, such as China and Thailand, which have taken more than 5 years to reach the figures India currently holds. The number of mobile phone subscribers in the country would exceed 50 million by 2010 and cross 300 million by 2016, according to Cellular Operators Association of India.

According to recent strategies research by Indian Cellular Services market, suchgrowth rates can be greatly attributed to the drastically falling price of mobile handsets with price playing a fundamental role in Indian subscriber requirements. Subscribers in certain region can acquire the handset at almost no cost. This should lead to increased subscribership. This market is growing at an extremely fast pace and so it led to the competition between the mobile service providers.

Reliance JioInfocomm Limited, a subsidiary of Reliance Industries Limited, India's Largest private sector company, is the first telecom operator to held pan India Unified License. Jio will provide 4G services on Pan-India level using LTE technology.

Objectives of the study

- To analyze the socio- economic profile of the Reliance Jio subscribers.
- To study the consumer's satisfaction regarding the services provided by Reliance Jio.
- To study the reasons for switching over to Reliance Jio.
- To suggest measures to effective marketing ofReliance Jio.

Data Collection

This study is based on primary data. The primary data were collected by the researcher and the field work was conducted. A questionnaire containing 32 questions were used as a data collection tool. The questionnaire is used to collect the options of user's attitude towards mobile phones.

Sample Size and Method

The sample size for this study is 50 and the method for selection is convenience sampling. The study is confined to only mobile phone users particularly subscribers of Reliance Jio and the samples are chosen from the area K. Pudur in Madurai City.

Tools Adopted

Data analyzing in this study is carried out through statistical tools which include percentage analysis, weighted average and chi-square.

Data Analysis and Interpretations

Table 1
Subscribers of any other mobile before opting Data Analysis

Subscriber for competition	No.of respondent	Percentage
Vodafone	6	12
Airtel	9	18
BSNL	12	24
RelianceJio	13	26
Aircel	10	20
Total	50	100

Source: computed from primary data

Table - 1 shows that 12% of the respondents are subscriber of Vodafone, 18% are subscriber of Airtel, 24% are BSNL 26% are Reliance and 20% of the respondents are subscriber of Aircel. Most of the respondents 26% are RelianceJio. Due to the features provided by the Aircel are upto the consumer expectations, 80% of the respondents switched over to Aircel.

Table 2
Reason for switching over to Reliance Jio

Reasons	No.of respondents	Percentage
Free calling service	12	24
Free Data uses	18	36
Free and easy available	11	22
Others	9	18
Total	50	100

Source: computed from primary data

Table - 2 shows that 24% of the respondents switching over to Reliance Jio mobile for free calling service, 36% of the respondents for free data uses, 22% for free and easy available and 18%

for other reasons. Most of the respondents 36% have willingness to switch over to Reliance Jio because of free data uses provided by Reliance Jio. Out of 50 respondents, 41 respondents said that all the basic factors, ie, free calling service, free data uses, free and easy available were attract them towards Reliance Jio.

Table - 3
Satisfaction level of respondents regarding Network Service

Opinion	No. of respondents	Percentage	Weight assigned(x)	Weighted average (wx)
Highly satisfied	18	36	5	90
Satisfied	14	28	4	56
Moderate	11	33	3	33
Dissatisfied	6	12	2	12
Highly dissatisfied	1	2	1	1
Total	50	100	15	191

Source: computed from primary data

$$\text{Weighted average} = (\sum wx) / (\sum w) = 191 / 50 = 3.84$$

The weighted average of 3.84 reveals that most of the respondents opinion was satisfied about the network service due to technological development.

Table – 4
Satisfaction level of respondents regarding Customer Care Service

Opinion	No. of respondents	Percentage	Weight assigned (x)	Weighted average (wx)
Highly satisfied	21	42	5	105
Satisfied	17	34	4	68
Moderate	9	18	3	27
Dissatisfied	2	4	2	4
Highly dissatisfied	1	2	1	1
Total	50	100	15	205

Source: computed from primary data

$$\text{Weighted average} = (\sum wx) / (\sum w) = 205 / 50 = 4.1$$

The weighted average of 4.1 shows that 34% of the respondents are satisfied with customer care services due to remarkable services rendered by Reliance Jio company.

Table 5
Relationship between monthly income and Consumer's preference about Reliance Jio Features

Monthly income in Rs.	Pocket internet	Full talk time	SMS	Total
Below 5000	--	14	11	25
5000 - 10000	--	7	5	12
10000 - 15000	2	3	--	5
Above 15000	8	--	--	8
Total	10	24	16	50

Source: computed from primary data

Ho - There is no significant relationship between monthly income and benefits offered by Reliance Jio.

H1 - Jio is being popular and favourite network connection among customers of telecom industry.

CHI Square Test

$$X^2 = \sum [(O-E)^2/E] : E = (\text{Row total} \times \text{column total}) / (\text{Total No. of observations})$$

O	E	O-E	(O-E) ²	(O-E) ² /E
2	1	1	1	1
8	1.6	6.4	40.96	25.6
14	5	9	81	16.2
7	5.76	2.56	6.55	1.14
3	2.4	0.60	0.36	0.15
11	8	3	9	1.13
5	3.84	1.16	1.3	0.34
Total				44.56

Source: computed from primary data

Calculated Value = 44.56

Degrees of freedom

$$V = (r-1)(c-1)$$

$$= (4-1)(3-1)$$

Total value = 12.59

Since calculated value is greater than table value, the hypothesis is rejected. Hence there is significant relationship between monthly income and benefits offered by Reliance Jio. It reveals that income of the consumer is one of the economic factors which determine the purchasing power of the consumers.

Findings

- 64% of the respondents are male users.
- 36% of the respondents are in the age group between 31-35 years.
- 28% of the respondents are Government employees.
- 56% of the respondents are unmarried.
- 50% of the respondents are belong to the monthly income level of below R. 5000 category

6. 48% of the respondents are spending less than 3 days outside hometown in a month.
7. 86% of the respondents carry their mobile when they are out of home town.
8. 80% of the respondents are subscriber of competitor before opting Reliance Jio.
9. 58% of the respondents want to change the mobile.
10. 72% of the respondents are willing to switch over to other mobile because of coverage.
11. 72% of the respondents own samsung handset.
12. 36% of the respondents are satisfied regarding Reliance Jio free data uses.
13. 24% of the respondents are satisfied regarding free calling service.
14. 50% of the respondents are satisfied regarding customer care service.
15. 58% of the respondents have no opinion regarding value added service.
16. 44% of the respondents are satisfied regarding roaming facility
17. 42% of the respondents have no opinion regarding roaming charges.
18. 22% of the respondents have no opinion regarding Network Service and 28% are satisfied.
19. 55% of the respondents are satisfied regarding plan.
20. 64% of the respondents are satisfied regarding availability of recharge coupon and 34% are highly satisfied.
21. 32% of the respondents are satisfied regarding SMS.
22. 44% of the respondents are satisfied regarding pulse rate.
23. 38% of the respondents are satisfied regarding rate cutter.
24. 56% of the respondents are purchasing coupon for Rs.399.
25. 30% of the respondents prefer Reliance Jio for good tower coverage.

Suggestions

Majority of the respondents are the subscribers who use of Reliance Jio and most of them report that they have chosen Reliance Jio because of coverage, roaming facility, availability of recharge coupon etc. Introduction of new features are welcomed among users. They also expect advanced facilities to ease effective communication, such as wider coverage, no roaming charges and more convenient plans.

The advertising strategy of Reliance Jio is good to make it popular among mobile phone users. However the competition is severe, from the public sector company BSNL and other private sector giants like Vodafone, Airtel, TataIndicom etc. Hence it is suggested that the Reliance Jio company should plan and propagate more flexible and attractive schemes to the present customers to prevent them from switching over to other brands and to attract prospective customers.

Conclusion

The Indian mobile telephony market has grown at a rapid speed in the last decade. Declining the call tariffs and favorable regulatory policies has led to a tremendous increase in the subscribers' base. Proper identification of the Customer preferences will facilitate the favorableness towards the various mobile service providers. Continuous research on customers will enhance the customer satisfaction.

The present study has been carried out to find out the most preferred mobile network service provider and the factors influencing to use the particular mobile network service. The results revealed that Jio network connection the most preferred mobile network service providers after launch in the market. Service quality, value added services and customer care service are the most influencing factors in the selection of a particular mobile network service providers and it would certainly help to improve the service quality of the mobile network service providers and also it improves the level of satisfaction of the mobile network users.

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